

PHYSICAL REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN IN THE EARLY PERIOD AFTER OSTEOSYNTHESIS WITH ELASTIC STERGEN

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Abstract. *The given article presents a system of rehabilitation measures for patients in the early postoperative period with closed femoral shaft fractures. The study involved 15 patients. The patients were aged 8-14 years. Of these, 3 (20%) were girls and 12 (80%) were boys. The sequence of physical education classes is described and a set of exercises is presented. The set of rehabilitation measures should be dynamic, taking into account the characteristics of a specific clinical condition and a gradual increase in physical activity.*

Keywords: *osteosynthesis, intraosseous elastic femoral rod, early rehabilitation.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that rehabilitation after surgical treatment of femoral fractures in children is a complex and urgent problem. Femoral shaft fractures account for 60-65% of all fractures in this segment [4]. The system of medical rehabilitation of patients continues from the moment the victim is admitted to a medical institution until complete recovery. Today, medical rehabilitation is one of the priority areas of healthcare development in the world [5]. In the last decade, elastic osteosynthesis of the sternum has taken a leading position in the surgical treatment of diaphyseal fractures of the femur in children.

Definitely, the main requirements for modern osteosynthesis are: minimally invasive surgical intervention, elimination of prolonged additional immobilization in the postoperative period [1], the possibility of early, active painless movement in the operated leg joints, and provision of dosed loading. Due to that, elastic-structure osteosynthesis in children entered clinical practice as a method that best meets the stated requirements of surgical treatment of diaphyseal fractures of long truncal bones, as well as legs, many authors consider it a "golden" standard of treatment [2, 3].

According to leading specialists in the field of medical rehabilitation, errors and omissions in the treatment of patients with pathologies of the musculoskeletal system often most likely occur in the postoperative period of rehabilitation treatment [6]. Late medical rehabilitation of patients is carried out by qualified rehabilitation specialists, and in the postoperative period rehabilitation measures are carried out by traumatologists, since the early postoperative period begins the period from the moment of surgery to the patient's discharge from the hospital.

Certainly, the efforts of these specialists are combined, and rehabilitation in the broadest sense of the word is achieved by restoring both the structure and functionality of the superficial segments of the musculoskeletal system. Our research was conducted at the Republican Center specialized in traumatology and orthopedic science and practical medicine.

Purpose, objectives, materials and methods of work:

The whole research is considered as the creation of a single approach to rehabilitative procedures in the early postoperative period after the completion of osteosynthesis of the elastic chest at the fracture of the femoral shaft and diaphysis.

What is more important, in 2020-2023, osteosynthesis with an elastic rod was performed for diaphyseal fractures of the femur at the Republican Specialized Traumatology and Orthopedic Scientific and Practical Medical Center. Elastic intramedullary rods of the ChM (Poland) and Double Medical (China) brands were used as fixators. In order to reduce the rehabilitation period of patients during the postoperative recovery period, early activation was carried out using therapeutic physical training complexes. The age of patients ranged from 8 to 14 years; the average age was 11.7 ± 2.1 years ($n = 15$). Of the victims, 3 were girls (20%), 12 – boys (80%). Closed fractures were observed in all patients. According to the AO classification, the patients were distributed by fracture type as follows: type A - 12 children (80.0%), type V - 2 children (13.3%), type C - 1 child (0.07%). Most surgeries are performed within 5-14 days after the injury. In the preoperative period, a Böhler splint was applied to the injured leg and a skeletal traction system with a load of 3-7 kg along the axis was installed to eliminate contractile movement of the thigh muscles and longitudinal displacement of fragments. For stretching, the needle was inserted through the tuberosity of the tibia or the distal metaphysis of the femur. All surgeries were performed under general and spinal anesthesia on an orthopedic table with retrograde installation of an elastic stent into the bone canal under the control of an electron-optical converter. In 13 (86.7%) cases, an elastic rod was installed without opening the fracture zone. In the postoperative period, a removable posterior longitudinal plaster cast was applied (Fig. 1, 2 and 3).

Figure 1. Patient I., 11 years old, closed fracture of the middle third of the right femur.

Figure 2. 1.5 and 6 months after surgery

Figure 3. A year after surgery (metal products removed)

Results of the study.

Due to the results the choice of the method of osteosynthesis with elastic stergen for fractures of the femur shaft in children involves early patient activity and ensuring the correct quality of life with a good functional result. Methods of early restorative treatment are aimed not only at preventing postoperative complications, but also at active restorative treatment in a mode of constantly increasing load. In our study, we were guided by the generally accepted classification of rehabilitation periods [6]:

- 1) the early postoperative period, from the moment of surgery and continues until the patient is discharged from the hospital (1-2 weeks);
- 2) the immediate postoperative period - from the moment of discharge from the hospital to 1.5-2 months after surgery (treatment at home and in outpatient settings);
- 3) the late postoperative period - the time of gradual restoration of functions and the ability to lean on the operated leg (2-3 months from the date of surgery);
- 4) the period of functional recovery - begins from the moment of restoration of the ability to lean on the body until full social and labor rehabilitation (3-8 months after surgery).

Comprehensive treatment of patients included a standardized scheme of activities. The goals of early rehabilitation treatment are:

- 1) early mobilization of the patient in bed;
- 2) 3-5 days after surgery (depending on the type of fracture) - passive movements and self-care skills in the hip and knee joints by removing the long ligament;
- 3) the use of therapeutic physical culture methods for rapid restoration of the function of the injured leg;
- 4) prevention of early and late complications after osteosynthesis of diaphyseal fractures of the femur;
- 5) preparation of the patient for the next stage of outpatient rehabilitation.

Definitely, at the end of the surgery, after transferring the patient to the ward, a removable posterior plaster cast was applied from the tip of the finger to the upper part of the thigh, bending the knee joint at an angle of 15° . A small pillow was placed under the knee joint. Since preoperative skeletal traction was performed behind the tuberosity of the tibia with extension of the knee joint capsule, this position of the leg reduced additional pain impulses. According to the patient's subjective sensations (by the end of the action of the anesthetic), it was recommended to perform active movements of the fingers for 1-3 minutes synchronously with movements on the healthy

leg. The exercises were initially performed with a small amplitude in easier conditions, and as the range of motion increased, with the maximum possible amplitude. From the 1st day of the postoperative period, it was recommended to perform kinesiotherapy of healthy legs against the background of breathing exercises. During physical training, slow movements were used in the form of knee flexion, palm flexion, hip flexion.

It is not a secret that starting from the 2nd day after the operation, special attention was paid to teaching patients isometric gymnastics aimed at maintaining muscle tone and improving blood circulation in the operated leg. Since the quadriceps muscle is often hypotrophied with this injury, the training included isometric stretching of this muscle, which helped prevent hypotrophy, improve the shortening function and increase tone. After open reposition, the presence of drains in the postoperative wound (tubular drains brought out through the skin through separate holes using an active aspiration system) is not considered a contraindication to isometric gymnastics, which contributed to the evacuation of the hematoma and discharge from the wound. Isometric exercises were performed 3-4 sessions with 3-6 loads per day according to generally accepted rules - maximum load, then twice as much rest. Active-passive movements were also performed in the knee joint of the operated leg in the angular range of 180° - 160° , and with closed osteosynthesis, the range of motion was increased until pain appeared.

An approximate set of physical exercises recommended for the patient from the second to the fourth day after surgery (initial position (IP) - lying on the back, arms along the body):

- 1) raise your arms up - inhale, return to - exhale 3-5 times;
- 2) bend the palms of the feet and write 6-10 times;
- 3) bend in the knee joints on the healthy side (legs move along the plane of the bed) 3-5 times;
- 4) turn the torso to the right and left, arms slide along the body;
- 5) isometric tension of the muscles of the thigh and buttocks 3-5 times for 5-7 seconds;
- 6) bend your arms at the elbows 6-10 times and write;
- 7) bend and unclench your fingers 6-10 times;
- 8) d. hour - lying on your back, arms bent at the elbows; arching in the thoracic spine, then, holding the Balkan frame, raise and lower the torso 3-5 times;
- 9) spread your arms to the sides - inhale, return to the starting position for an hour - exhale 6-10 times.

Besides that, the exercises were performed at a calm pace without holding your breath. We recommend performing this set of exercises 2-3 times a day for 3-5 minutes. If the patient's general condition is satisfactory, exercises with weights and additional weights are added (the patient performs leg movements, and the attending physician resists the movement). Later, the duration of the exercises is increased to 10 minutes, and the number of repetitions is increased to 5-6 times a day.

From 4-5 days after the operation, patients are allowed to sit in an upright position with their legs down and feet on the floor 6-8 times a day (while eating in a sitting position). In this case, the angle of flexion in the knee joint is 15° - 20° . Activation is carried out taking into account an individual approach to a specific patient, his orthostatic reaction, age, somatic condition and blood loss during surgery.

As a rule, from the 5th day the patient is taught to get out of bed on crutches, first with someone's help, and then independently, leaning on the healthy leg. The patients leaned on a crutch

next to the bed, leaning their body weight on the healthy leg, and moved around the ward (5-6 steps). In the coming days, the skills of walking with crutches will appear. The stitches are removed on the 12th-14th day after the operation. By the time of discharge from the hospital on the 12th-14th day, patients in this group can confidently walk 25-30 meters without leaning on the operated leg, using crutches. When walking with crutches, patients are advised to pay attention to maintaining the walking stereotype, active alignment of the joints, the exclusion of the flexion-rotation position with passive stabilization of the knee joint. Compliance with these recommendations on the movement regimen allows patients to independently regulate the load upon discharge from the hospital and is the basis for its subsequent expansion in outpatient settings.

Conclusions

By summarizing it should be suggested that the complex of rehabilitation treatment measures in the early postoperative period in patients after osteosynthesis of the femoral shaft in children should be dynamic, taking into account the gradual increase in physical activity and the characteristics of a specific clinical condition. As a rule, by the end of the period, patients should move with crutches, without loading the operated leg, and actively hold the leg in the knee joint. A correctly selected mode of movement, load during movement, as well as the skills of therapeutic physical exercises obtained under the guidance of the attending traumatologist, will form the basis for subsequent rehabilitation measures of patients, which is expected that further research will be carried out in the direction of studying other problems of physical rehabilitation in the early period of osteosynthesis with an elastic string for fractures of the femoral shaft in children.

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